

Paskuwatti's Ritual to Cure Sexual Dysfunction

Expert source: Billie Collins, Lockwood Press

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

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** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Hittite, Ritual Manual, Prayer, Religious Group, Anatolian Religions, Text, Ritual inscriptions, Language, Hittite Religions, Ritual text, Indo-European, Anatolian, Hittite

Paskuwatti's ritual is an invitation to the Hittite goddess Uliliyassi to assist a man who is unable to perform sexually with a woman. The ritual manuscript is a detailed description, told in the first person, of the ritual performed by Paskuwatti, an Arzawan woman (of far west Anatolia, or what is modern-day Turkey). Only one manuscript of the ritual has survived, KUB 7.8 + KUB 9.27 (+) KUB 7.5 (CTH 406), which dates to the thirteenth century. However, the composition itself was likely first written ca. 1400 BCE. The manuscript tablet's findspot is not known. Because there is one known extant copy of the original composition, no variations in the ritual are known. Some of the motifs and themes within the ritual reflect those of other rituals within the Hittite tradition and culture, but the composition is unique in terms of its purpose as well as its form, with an extended prayer embedded within the ritual description. The composition was recorded by Paskuwatti and acquisitioned by Hittite scribes at the direction of their king – suggesting that the ritual was deemed significant by the royal house as a suitable intervention in the case that a male member of the house was unable to perform sexually. In this sense, the ritual is used as needed for the cure of sexual disfunction. The ritual itself is performed by Paskuwatti in three days' time. All that are involved are Paskuwatti, an assistant, and the patient. It begins in the patient's home, where the materials necessary for the ritual are prepared, and then the rites are performed away from human habitation. Incantations and offering rites to Uliliyassi are performed in alternating sequence as the goddess is invited to aid the patient by having sex with him. Next, the patient returns home for an incubation period in which he hopes that Uliliyassi appears to him in his dreams. The incubation period involves entreaties to the goddess, sacrifice of a sheep for a ritual meal, and checking in with the ritualist to report on the goddess's appearance. The ritual is repeated if it fails. The patient promises that he will worship Uliliyassi as his personal goddess if he is cured of sexual impotence.

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: Boğazkale, Turkey

Region tags: Asia Minor, Boğazkale, Middle East, Anatolia, Turkey

Boğazkale, Turkey (ancient Hattusa)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mouton, Alice. “Rituel de Paškuwatti d'Arzawa (CTH 406).” https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/intro.php?xst=CTH%20406&prgr=&lg=FR&ed=A.%20Mouton
- Source 1: Collins, Billie Jean. “Paskuwatti’s Ritual to Cure Sexual Dysfunction (CTH 406).” In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>

Notes: Collins, Billie Jean. “Paskuwatti’s Ritual to Cure Sexual Dysfunction (CTH 406).” In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 2 URL: https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/intro.php?xst=CTH%20406&prgr=&lg=FR&ed=A.%20Mouton
- Source 2 Description: Mouton, Alice. “Rituel de Paškuwatti d'Arzawa (CTH 406).”

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Notes: Incised

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Method of inscription

- Other [specify]: Stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Clay

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Clay object

– Clay tablet

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Library/archive

– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: It uses a literary/religious register of language

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 4

Notes: Four people - including the ritualist, her assistant, the patient, and the goddess (Uliliyassi). Royal scribes or members of the royal family may have been a secondary audience to the ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 4

Notes: See notes above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 4

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Yes

Notes: The invocation in the text is directed to the goddess Uliliyassi.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Is it read?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The ritual is produced to "cure" a man who is unable to perform sexually with a woman

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 3

Notes: The ritualist, ritualist's assistant, and the patient

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Seemingly as needed and able to be employed for the ritual purpose

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is accompanied by a variety of ritual actions, including offerings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Reference to galaktar and parhuena, which may be intoxicants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The incubation period after the invocation of the goddess includes entreaties to her -- one of which being the sacrifice of a sheep in preparation for a ritual meal, but it is unclear based on the ritual text's description who would have consumed the meal offered.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: This text was included in the Hittite royal archives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: It belongs to a large corpus of ritual texts maintained for royal use.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text is a script for Paskuwatti's ritual cure for sexual impotence and is, in this sense, a manual for the ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: An afterlife is not mentioned in the text as its concern is purely a this-worldly affair.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: This is not specified within the text. However, it must be the case that the ritual can be practiced as needed throughout the region.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: The ritual does not make a distinction between hidden vs. plain and performed motivations of the patient and/or ritualist.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Other?

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: An offering of food is presented.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: However, the Hittite pantheon forms the background of the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Notes: No, but she only appears to the patient because her presence is only requested of him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Libations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Food?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Daily life objects?

– Yes

Notes: These include a spindle, distaff, reeds, and a bow and arrow, but they are not specifically offered to the goddess.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: However, some have suggested that this is a ritual to counter non-masculine behavior or homosexuality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: Not relevant to the text if so

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Notes: Not mentioned/relevant within the text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Notes: Not mentioned/relevant within the text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Adultery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Incest

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: The performance of sex will cure sexual dysfunction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Considering that the patient makes promises to the goddess if she appears to him, yes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Quite the opposite

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 8

Notes: The ritual is performed three times per day until effective.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: Food offerings are made, including one soldier bread, three sweet thick breads with specified ingredients, a tuft of lambswool, and a pitcher of wine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ By the community?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance is required of the participants described above - the ritualist, her assistant, and the patient - while attendance by the goddess is hoped for in invoking her.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: A scribal school

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Turkey

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General References

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